

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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List of Acronyms

AIA	The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (of SDO)
AU	Astronomical Unit
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COR	Coronagraph
EPHIN	The Electron Proton Helium Instrument
EUI	Extreme Ultraviolet Imager
EUVI	Extreme UltraViolet Imager
EUV	Extreme Ultraviolet
HI	Heliospheric Imager
IRAP	Institute of Research in Astrophysics and Planetology
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
LASCO	Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph Experiment
MAST	Magnetohydrodynamics Around a Sphere Thermodynamic
MHD	MagnetoHydroDynamic
PSI	Predictive Sciences Inc
PSP	Parker Solar Probe
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SDO	Solar Dynamics Observatory
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SQ	Science Question
STEREO	Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
UPS	Université Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier
UT	Universal Time
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
WISPR	Wide Imager of PSP

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The debate regarding the primary acceleration mechanism of Solar Energetic Particle ([SEP](#)) events centers on whether the dominant process is flare-associated magnetic reconnection and rapid particle acceleration in reconnection regions, or diffusive shock acceleration at Coronal Mass Ejection ([CME](#))-driven shock fronts, with current evidence supporting a complex interplay between both mechanisms depending on the energy range and event characteristics. The aim of this task and its associated deliverable, at hand, was to provide detailed information on coronal shock waves that develop during a subset of the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data ([SPEARHEAD](#)) catalogue of >100 MeV proton events ([Vainio et al. 2024](#)), with particular emphasis on the [GLE](#) events - the most energetic [SEP](#) events detected near Earth. To derive detailed information on the shocks, we conducted 3-D shock reconstructions using multi-point images and the multi-dimensional SHOCK3D modelling technique developed by Université Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier ([UPS](#)). Combined with full 3-D [MHD](#) modelling of the corona, this method derives key shock parameters such as Mach numbers, compression ratios, and shock normal angles by combining the velocity obtained from 3-D fitting with properties of the background corona and solar wind provided by global [MHD](#) models. The [MAST](#) 3-D [MHD](#) model of the corona was used to supply the necessary plasma conditions for this analysis. Additionally, these models help determine when and where a spacecraft is magnetically connected to a shock by tracing magnetic field lines from the spacecraft back to the shock surface within the 3-D [MHD](#) framework. This document explains the method used in the creation of this shock catalogue and further provides details for the [SPEARHEAD](#)'s case studies of the recent [GLE](#) events of 2024.

1 Introduction

3-D modelling of the shock surrounding Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) observed in coronal imagery can only be done when several coronal imaging detectors observe the solar corona from different vantage points. This was only possible after 2006 when the Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) spacecraft were launched and provided at least a second viewpoint to base our CME triangulation on. There are currently 84 events in the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) catalogue of >100 MeV protons (Vainio et al. 2024) after 2006. It should be noted that the 3-D shock modelling process is performed manually and requires considerable attention to detail. As such, it is a time-intensive task and cannot feasibly be conducted for all 84 events. Nonetheless, within the SPEARHEAD project, we prepared a comprehensive catalogue of modelled shocks, developed through two key tasks, which encompasses:

- *Sub-task 4.3.1:* Three new Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) events that occurred during the SPEARHEAD project so far (GLEs 74, 75, 76). Should more GLEs occur until the end of the project, those will also be considered in this analysis.
- *Sub-task 4.3.2:* A detailed comparison and association of our shock fittings carried out before the SPEARHEAD project with the >100 MeV catalogue event.

2 MHD shocks

When CMEs travel outward from the Sun, they undergo significant expansion due to their strong internal magnetic fields and the decreasing pressure of the surrounding solar wind. This expansion occurs both laterally and radially, causing the CME to grow in size and potentially impact a broader area. Compression occurs on the front of the CME when it moves faster than the surrounding medium. This wave pressure intensifies causing a progressive steepening of the front portion of the wave. A shock wave forms when this pressure wave moves faster than the local characteristic speeds (Alfvén and magnetosonic speeds) of the coronal and interplanetary plasma. When the pressure wave has a large enough amplitude, non-linear effects become important and complex kinetic plasma processes will allow a shock discontinuity to develop despite the collisionless nature of the medium. The gradients of pressure, density, temperature, and velocity increase and become so large that dissipative processes, such as viscosity or thermal conduction, are no longer negligible. Then a steady wave-shape, called a shock wave, can appear, with a balance between the steepening effect of the non-linear convective terms and the broadening effect of dissipation.

The outermost surface of CMEs, where pressure waves form that potentially steepen into shock waves, have been shown to follow an ellipsoid geometry (see details in Jarry et al. 2023). By fitting the CME outermost boundary on successive images and from several vantage points simultaneously, the position and dimensions of the ellipsoid can be determined. Such shock wave 3-D reconstructions offer a lot of advantages, such as going beyond the projection effects to track its height and speed in the corona more accurately and in 3-D.

2.1 Selection of events

3-D reconstruction of shocks associated with CMEs requires simultaneous coronal imaging from multiple viewpoints to accurately resolve their geometry and evolution. Such multi-perspective observations only became routinely available following the 2006 launch of the STEREO mission, which provided an additional line of sight essential for reliable CME and shock triangulation. Within this context, the SPEARHEAD catalogue contains 84 greater than 100 MeV proton events recorded since the start of the STEREO era.

Because the 3-D shock reconstruction must be performed manually and involves a high level of precision and scrutiny, it is an inherently time-consuming process. Consequently, a full analysis could not be carried out for every event in the catalogue. This constraint was anticipated in the original **SPEARHEAD** proposal; hence, Deliverable 4.3 concentrated on priority events, namely all **GLEs** observed since the start of the **STEREO** mission (after 2006) and the shocks listed as priorities in Deliverable (Rouillard et al. 2024). This includes the last three **GLE** events that occurred after the project started. Namely, **GLE74** on 11 May 2024 (Papaioannou et al. 2025), **GLE75** on 08 June 2024 (Poluianov et al. 2025), and **GLE76** on 21 November 2024¹.

2.2 3-D shock modelling

The advent of coronal and solar wind imaging from multiple vantage points, thanks to the **STEREO** spacecraft, revolutionized the monitoring and modelling of **CMEs** and their associated shock fronts. This mission provided the first continuous multi-viewpoint remote-sensing observations of the Sun and corona, enabling the development of techniques to track the 3-D evolution of shock waves by fitting their geometry from different vantage points (Kwon et al. 2015; Rouillard et al. 2016; Kwon & Vourlidas 2017). In the present analysis, we used the technique developed in Rouillard et al. (2016), which consists in fitting shock waves in 3-D using multipoint imagery to derive the velocity field of each point on the expanding pressure wave/shock.

Figure 1: Sequence of **STEREO-B** Extreme UltraViolet Imager (**EUVI**) 195 Å images from Veronig et al. (2010) showing the early wave evolution on the disk and above the limb (top panels: direct images; middle and bottom panels: 5-minutes running difference images). The dome shape is easily visible on images at 03:56 and 04:01 Universal Time (**UT**). In the sixth panel, the outer contours of the coronal dimming are highlighted.

¹<https://gle.oulu.fi/>

Reconstructing shock waves in 3-D offers significant benefits, such as overcoming projection effects inherent to optically-thin coronal imaging, enabling a more precise determination of the shock's height and velocity in the corona. All available spacecraft imagery (STEREO/EUVI/Coronagraph (COR)1/COR2/Heliospheric Imager (HI)1/2), Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) C2/C3, Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO)/The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA), Parker Solar Probe (PSP)/Wide Imager of (WISPR) and Solar Orbiter (SolO)/Extreme Ultraviolet Imager (EUI)/METIS/HI) is typically considered for these detailed analyses.

The 3-D triangulation technique consists in tracking the region perturbed by the outermost extent of pressure front visible in the coronal images (Kwon et al. 2015; Rouillard et al. 2016). This area is generally characterised by a visible bubble in Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) and white-light imagery, alongside a wavefront observable on the solar disk in EUV images (like in Fig. 1). This wavefront marks the junction between the 3-D bubble and the yet undisturbed coronal area just above, imaged in EUV and white light. The pressure wave system is then tracked as the outer boundary of the region affected by the CME as it emerges and expands within the corona. Regions of the pressure wave's surface moving faster than the local characteristic speed of the coronal medium are potential sites for shock wave formation. Kwon et al. (2015); Rouillard et al. (2016) have shown that shock waves observed from multiple vantage points can be well reproduced geometrically by simple ellipsoids. The multi-viewpoint imaging offer a robust fitting of the radial and lateral expansion of the pressure wave.

In Fig. 2, we show a schematic of the ellipsoid model fitted to the EUV and white-light images in running difference to obtain the reconstructed shock wave. The ellipsoid has three half-major axes: $a(t)$ in the radial direction, and $b(t)$ and $c(t)$ for its cross-radial (or lateral) dimensions. An example result of shock wave fit is shown in Fig. 3, with the modelled ellipsoid represented by the red dashed lines on running difference white-light images.

Figure 2: Schematics of the shock wave fit. The parameters displayed are those of the ellipsoid model: r (blue dashed line) represents the distance between the surface of the Sun and the centre of the ellipsoid; a , b , and c (green dashed lines) are the half-axes; V_R and V_L (red lines) represent its radial and lateral speeds, respectively. The shock wave is represented by a half-sphere for illustrative purposes, i.e., $a(t) \sim b(t) \sim c(t)$ between 2 and 25 solar radii.

In the shock model, the upstream background is usually modelled using 3-D MagnetoHydroDynamic (MHD) models. The downstream region is the sheath region compressed by the magnetic piston, usually taking the form of a magnetic flux ropes.

The accuracy of the imagery-based shock fitting procedure depends on (1) the general availability of simultaneous observations from at least two viewpoints, (2) the overall cadence of the imaging, (3) the existence of previous events and the overall contamination of images (by high energy particles), and (4) the separation angle of the viewpoints with respect to the source region. That is why we generally stop the fitting at 20-25 solar radii.

Kouloumvakos et al. (2019) improved and exploited the previously described approach to model the evolution of 33 shock waves observed during the STEREO era. They selected 33 CMEs between 2011 and 2017 that produced strong pressure waves in the solar corona during their eruption associated with significant concomitant Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events. *The present deliverable has extended this catalogue.* The events considered were typically observed simultaneously by several white-light and ultraviolet imagers, for example SDO, SOHO/Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph Experiment (LASCO) and the two STEREOs (STEREO-A and STEREO-B). Application of the triangulation technique enabled a reconstruction of the time-evolving 3-D ellipsoidal shape of each pressure wave, leading to the catalogue of 3-D shock properties. Figure 3 presents an example of the shock-fitting technique applied to the powerful 23 July 2012 event by exploiting combined STEREO and SOHO data. This very clear CME shock event has been analysed in a number of past studies (e.g. Liu et al. 2014; Temmer & Nitta 2015).

Figure 3: Example to describe shock-wave triangulation using three different viewpoints for the 23 July 2012 event. Left top: White-light images from three points of view of a halo CME in white-light, with STEREO-A, SOHO/LASCO, and STEREO-B (shown from left to right). Left bottom: Same images in running difference. Red dashed lines show the shape of a reconstructed shock wave. Right: Spacecraft positions at the CME eruption time. The CME propagation direction is indicated by a black arrow. This panel is produced using Solar-MACH (Gieseler et al. 2023).

2.3 Deriving MHD parameters of shocks

The number of fast CMEs, which are driving strong shock waves in the solar corona, is always significantly larger than the number of relativistic particle events actually observed, and it is presently an open question which properties of the shock or the ambient medium (if any) can make a fast CME efficient in accelerating particles to relativistic energies either for the proton or the electron case. A few explanations have been suggested, e.g., (i) coronal magnetic field geometry in different parts of the shock may favour particle acceleration to very high energies only if the observer is connected to these parts of the shock (Sandroos & Vainio 2009; Frassati et al. 2022); or (ii) the high variability of the shock strength on the global coronal shock front, with only certain parts of it demonstrating high Mach numbers favourable for particle acceleration (Rouillard et al. 2016; Kouloumvakos et al. 2020). All explanations rely on the special conditions of the medium through which the shock is propagating with its ambient magnetic field; it is of paramount importance to disentangle them.

The 3-D reconstruction provides the velocity of each point on the surface of the expanding shock. When combined with numerical models of the background solar corona and solar wind, the set of Rankine-Hugoniot equations of the shock jump conditions can be solved to derive the fundamental properties of the shock wave, such as the shock front speed, Mach number, or the angle of the shock nor-

mal with respect to the local magnetic field direction, θ_{BN} (Rouillard et al. 2016; Plotnikov et al. 2017). The coronal magneto properties are provided by the 3-D MHD cubes from the 3-D MHD coronal model developed by Predictive Sciences Inc (PSI) called Magnetohydrodynamics Around a Sphere Thermodynamic (MAST). These numerical simulations are available for the past 15 years on the PSI website. This provides valuable information for theorists wishing to test different theories of shock acceleration. For instance, the measurement of θ_{BN} is important because it is suspected to have an impact on the efficiency of particle acceleration by a propagating shock front and could explain the variability in SEP compositions (Tylka et al. 2005; Tylka & Lee 2006).

2.4 Field-line tracing:

Based on the shock modelling and a 3-D model of the background coronal and solar wind magnetic field, we can extract the history of the shock properties along magnetic field lines connected to several detectors (Jarry 2024). In this approach we suppose that the interplanetary magnetic field consists of a simple Parker spiral while the coronal magnetic field is provided by the 3-D MHD MAST cubes (Fig. 4). To extract the shock parameters along a given magnetic field line connected to a spacecraft, we need to estimate the point of intersection between the magnetic field line of interest and the shock surface. Since the SPEARHEAD project is focused on powerful SEPs measured near Earth, the evolving shock parameters (speed, Mach number, geometry, density compression ratio) are provided only along Earth-connected magnetic field lines.

Figure 4: 3-D representation of the field line tracing, using the Parker spiral model between the spacecraft/object location and 20 solar radii (yellow), and MAST cubes until 1 solar radius (orange). Field lines are connecting STEREO-A, the Earth, PSP and SolO, respectively in red, green, magenta and cyan.

3 The catalogue of shock waves

For each event, information given in the shock-fitting catalogue are time in UT, longitude and latitude in both Stonyhurst and Carrington heliographic coordinates, and two sets of ellipsoidal parameters. The first is called the $hek\alpha$ parameters, with $h(t)$ the altitude of the shock wave nose, $e(t)$ its eccentricity, $k(t)$ its shape factor and $\alpha(t)$ its transverse aspect ratio. The second set gives the same ellipsoid in a different system, called the $rabc$ parameters. This $rabc$ system is easier to visualise as $r(t)$ is the distance between the Sun and the centre of the ellipsoid, and $a(t)$, $b(t)$ and $c(t)$ are its three half-major axes. Next to these four parameters, we have a last one, called $tilt$, which is the angle associated to the orientation of the shock, because we allow all the structure of the shock wave to rotate on itself. Generally, $tilt(t)$ stays at zero during the event.

3.1 New shock fittings

This section presents the GLE events for which shock fittings were carried out for the SPEARHEAD project. The three GLE events are GLE74 (11 May 2024), GLE75 (08 June 2024), and GLE76 (21 November 2024); they are already presented briefly in Rouillard et al. (2024) and thus will not be repeated here. Instead, here we show the results of the shock fitting. Since STEREO-A was located near Earth in 2024, the combination of the Earth and STEREO-A vantage points was not as optimal and as a result some simplification was made in the fitting procedure. Ideally, a spacecraft separation of 40-120 degrees provides better constraints for 3-D triangulation of the sources (Rouillard et al. 2016). Our past work using such optimal configurations has shown that the heliocentric central axis of the shock ellipsoidal structure is close to the flaring source region of the CME (Jarry et al. 2024). We therefore used this as our starting point and adjusted this direction during the fitting for the GLEs under study. The imaging data exploited to carry out this fitting was STEREO-A EUVI, COR-1, COR-2, as well as SOHO/LASCO C2 and C3 and SDO/AIA. Figure 5 provides an illustration of the three fitted shocks. Each row shows examples of shock fits at different times when the apex of the CME was in still in the low corona in EUV imaging, and in the mid and high corona in coronagraphs.

The second step of the modelling provides the 3-D shock parameters of the shock over its entire surface by combining the velocity field derived from the previous triangulation work with 3-D MHD. Figure 5 shows a summary of the modelling results for the three events. Each row shows a specific event at a specific time, and three examples of modelled shock properties (speed, Mach, geometry) are shown in each column. Other modelled shock parameters include shock jump conditions (density and magnetic field compression ratios) obtained by solving the Rankine-Hugoniot relations.

The next step is field line tracing, as mentioned before, using Parker spiral model and MAST cubes, starting from the spacecraft/Earth location. Figure 6 shows the reconstructed field lines for the three GLEs events. Then for each time-step the intersection between the shock front and the field line is looked up (if it exists) and the values of the shock parameters at this intersection are recovered. Figure 7 shows for the example of GLE74 and GLE75 events a 3-D representation as seen from the solar north, of the shock wave and the Earth field line (green). The shock (represented by the bubble) is coloured according to the Alfvénic Mach number intensity, and its value is recovered at the intersection point with the field line.

A comprehensive analysis of these three events is currently underway, incorporating state-of-the-art combined shock modelling and particle transport simulations, with the results being prepared for publication in research articles to be submitted in 2026

Figure 5: Representation of the 3-D shock fitting for [GLE74](#) (panel a), [GLE75](#) (panel b), and [GLE76](#) (panel c). In each panel, the first line shows white light running differences images at three different times, while the second line shows the same images with the shock wave added as an orange bubble .

3.2 Listing of shock parameters along field lines connected to Earth:

These new shock modelling results have been combined within the master catalogue of shocks put in place and maintained by the Institute of Research in Astrophysics and Planetology ([IRAP](#)) over the past decade. With these additions, this catalogue now contains over 26 events. Based on the >100 MeV

Figure 6: View of the ecliptic from the solar north that shows the reconstructed MHD field lines connecting Earth (green), STEREO-A (red), PSP (purple), BepiColombo (yellow), and Solar Orbiter (blue), for, from left to right, the GLE74, GLE75 and GLE76 events. The sun is shown with the yellow circle, and the scale is in solar radii.

Figure 7: Same as Fig. 6, but showing only the Earth field line together with the fitted shock wave (bubble), coloured according to the Alfvénic Mach number intensity, for GLE74 and GLE75.

catalogue, we found 23 events that were fitted. We then followed the previously described methodology to extract MHD parameters along the magnetic field lines connected to the Earth environment for each event in the >100 MeV catalogue. Repeating this approach during the first hours of each event, we derived the time history of the shock parameters along the field line connected to Earth and stored this information in a new catalogue. The structure of this catalogue is shown in Fig. 8.

Time	Shock fit parameters				Shock parameters along L1/Earth FL			
	r	a	b	c	Shock speed	Mach Alfvénic	theta _{BN}	XR
UT	R _{sun}	R _{sun}	R _{sun}	R _{sun}	km/s	l	deg	l
08-Jun-2024 01:30:00	0.97	0.45	0.45	0.45	315.12	1.03	71.83	0.92
08-Jun-2024 01:31:00	0.99	0.46	0.46	0.46	398.8	1.28	64.59	1.24
08-Jun-2024 01:32:00	1.02	0.49	0.49	0.49	535.37	1.69	56.85	1.74
08-Jun-2024 01:33:00	1.04	0.52	0.52	0.52	735.7	2.28	50.33	2.37
08-Jun-2024 01:34:00	1.06	0.58	0.58	0.58	868.9	2.76	43.96	2.8
08-Jun-2024 01:35:00	1.09	0.63	0.63	0.63	760.47	2.51	38.45	2.68
08-Jun-2024 01:36:00	1.11	0.67	0.67	0.67	642.57	2.06	36.26	2.31
08-Jun-2024 01:37:00	1.13	0.7	0.7	0.7	693.65	2.25	33.66	2.54
08-Jun-2024 01:38:00	1.16	0.74	0.74	0.74	826.57	2.69	31.61	2.95
08-Jun-2024 01:39:00	1.18	0.8	0.8	0.8	954.57	3.33	28.68	3.34
08-Jun-2024 01:40:00	1.2	0.87	0.87	0.87	1060.56	3.78	27.01	3.51
08-Jun-2024 01:41:00	1.22	0.95	0.95	0.95	1154.62	4.21	24.39	3.64

Figure 8: Structure of the shock catalogue for the example of the GLE75 event (8 June 2024). The first column is the time in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), the next four are the shock fit parameters (r, a, b, c in solar radii). The last four columns are the derived MHD shock parameters evolution along the Earth field line: the shock speed, the Alfvénic Mach number, the magnetic field obliquity θ_{BN} , and the compression ratio X_R .

Figure 9: Proton peak intensity measured by The Electron Proton Helium Instrument (EPHIN) as a function of the first value at connection time (blue) and maximum (red) of the Alfvénic Mach number (panel a), shock speed (panel b), θ_{BN} (panel c), and X_R (panel d) derived for the Earth field line.

This catalogue provides to end-users of SPEARHEAD catalogues complementary information on the shock conditions close to the Sun. For instance, they may wish to test different theories of particle acceleration by comparing the intensity of SEPs or their spectral properties with the time varying shock Mach number or shock geometry. Figure 9 shows as an example the scatter plots of the maximum intensity of >100 MeV events with the maximum (first value at connection) parameters of the shock for each event in red (blue).

3.3 Future improvements:

Future improvements that are underway and were not envisaged in the proposal are a heliospheric extension of the 3-D MHD modelling. During the first part of the project, the Université Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier (UPS) team has put in place a heliospheric extension (0.1 to 1 Astronomical Unit (AU)) of the 3-D MHD MAST modelling. The 3-D MAST cubes that are used to model the shock can provide the solar wind conditions at its outer boundary that can be used as input at 0.1 AU to IRAP's heliospheric 3-D MHD model called HelioCast. The heliospheric extension provides a more self-consistent treatment of the magnetic field structure from the shock surface in the corona to the near-Earth environment. The team is working towards simulating the three recent GLEs this way, and time permitting more events will be integrated in the SPEARHEAD catalogue of shock modelling and magnetic connectivity. An example of this extra modelling work is shown in Figure 10, this has necessitated during the first part of the project to put in place a full pipeline of simulation processing (visualisation, field line tracing, in situ data visualisation,...) that is now nearly automated. Another evolution envisaged for (Rouillard et al. 2025) and is underway is to extend the shock modelling into the heliospheric domain as well. This can be carried out by using the shock modelling presented previously to initiate a shock at the inner boundary of the heliospheric simulation domain.

Figure 10: Left-hand panel: an example of a coronal shock modelling carried out in D4.3 from the solar surface to 0.1 AU. Middle panel: the result of the heliospheric model HelioCast extending from 0.1 to 1 AU showing the simulated solar wind speed in the ecliptic plane. The planets and probes located in that plane are shown together with their magnetic field lines connected to the lower corona. This heliospheric model propagates the background solar wind model used for the shock fitting and provides more self-consistent field line tracing. Right-hand panel: the propagation of shocks and CME flux ropes into the heliospheric domain by the HelioCast model showing the amplitude of the solar wind speed in the ecliptic plane. Work under development.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

This deliverable has achieved the main objective of compiling a comprehensive catalogue of three-dimensional (3-D) coronal shocks associated with high-energy SEP events, with a particular emphasis on GLEs — the most energetic SEP events observed near Earth. Through the combination of multi-point coronal imaging from SOHO, SDO, and STEREO with advanced three-dimensional MHD modelling, key physical parameters of the shocks were derived, including their speed, Mach number, magnetic obliquity, and compression ratio. **These results provide essential input for understanding the conditions under which coronal shocks accelerate particles to very high energies**, directly addressing the first Science Question (SQ) put forth by the project, namely:

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions?**

Within this 3-D MHD framework, the injection of energetic particles can be further investigated by tracing magnetic field lines from a spacecraft location back to the CME-driven shock surface. This approach enables the identification of regions along the shock front that are magnetically connected to the observer at a given time. When a spacecraft's magnetic field line intersects the shock, it reveals a potential pathway for accelerated particles to propagate from the shock region to the spacecraft. The timing and geometry of this magnetic connection determine when and how efficiently particles are injected and subsequently detected. **By combining the derived shock properties with field line tracing, it becomes possible to characterize the evolution of magnetic connectivity and assess the role of shock geometry—particularly the quasi-parallel and quasi-perpendicular configurations**, directly addressing the second SQ put forth by the project, namely:

- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release from acceleration sites in the solar corona?**

Special focus on this deliverable was put to the three GLEs that occurred during the first half of the SPEARHEAD project (GLE74, GLE75, and GLE76). Adding these along with earlier events from existing studies led to a catalogue of more than two dozen shocks associated to >100 MeV SEPs that are now characterised in a consistent framework, providing a valuable resource for both the SPEARHEAD consortium and the broader heliophysics community.

Future work will focus on extending the modelling framework by integrating the **MAST** coronal model with the Heliocast heliospheric simulation, allowing for a more complete and self-consistent description of magnetic connectivity from the low corona to near-Earth space. In parallel, the modelling and analysis pipeline is being automated to increase efficiency and to facilitate the incorporation of future **GLEs** and high-energy SEP events as they occur in the course of the project.

In summary, Deliverable D4.3 (Rouillard et al. 2025) provides the first version of the SPEARHEAD 3-D shock catalogue, delivering a key milestone towards the project's goals of investigating high-energy particle acceleration processes and injection in the heliosphere, and thus facilitating SQ1 and SQ2.

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